

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE EVALUATION SYSTEM: DEVELOPMENT OF TESTING IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Abstract: The article under discussion depicts a foreign experience in the evaluation system. A significant role in achieving the requirements for the results of student learning, in improving the educational process plays a test of knowledge and skills. The author of the article considers that at present much attention is paid to the psychological and pedagogical problems of testing (problems of anxiety, motivation), development of special procedures to identify the dimensionality of measurement space, the creation of special techniques, allowing a reasonable use of results of pedagogical measurements in education quality management.

Key words: assessment, test, teaching and learning process, modern, pedagogical concepts, rational use, testing students' knowledge.

One of the earliest attempts to create tests include the research of F. Galton and J. Cattell, who as early as 1890 used the term "mental intelligence test" (mental test). They are also credited with the introduction into scientific circulation the special characteristic of the quality of a test (power of discrimination), indicating its ability to differentiate test takers by measured variable [3]. However, the emergence of pedagogical tests abroad is often associated with the name of the French doctor and psychologist A. Binet and his work on the diagnosis of intellectual abilities. In 1905, A. Binet and T. Simon were the authors of the first practical intelligence test, called "Binet-Simon mental development scale". In 1916. L. Termen created new tests (Stanford-Binet), which are an original modification of the work of his predecessor. A little later, A. Binet's ideas were used by the German psychologist and philosopher W. Stern, who proposed a special coefficient for assessing

intelligence - the IQ coefficient. The term is still used today, although in a different context [2].

Achievements of the second decade of the 20th century in the field of measurements are considered to be the famous batteries of Alpha and Beta tests for the army. Thanks to a team of specialists including E. Thorndike, R. Goddard, P. Yerkes and L. Thurman, tests were created that have subsequently been used (up to the present time) as examples in the training of test developers in education. The first standardized meters in U.S. education were created to assess the quality of handwriting, spelling, and arithmetic in the late 1920s. America also had a battery of SAT tests designed to screen college applicants. Later, at the end of the 1940s there were created batteries of achievement tests, realizing the idea of multidimensional measurement and providing comparability of results on different school subjects [4].

In 1904 the Englishman C. Spearman published a fundamental theoretical work on the study of general intellectual abilities. Using school grades in various subjects, he applied to test data the apparatus of correlation theory, new for that time, and revealed examples of the covariance of schoolchildren's grades. In so doing, he laid the foundation for scientific approaches to the substantiation of test quality, combining in his study the theory of physical measurements, correlation methods, and the experience accumulated by his predecessor psychologists in evaluating children's abilities [7].

The prototype of the scientific provisions of the theory of pedagogical measurements was the far from educational work of N.R. Campbell "Fundamentals of Physics" (1920), thanks to which the theoretical apparatus for analyzing the quality of measurements was developed, and the commonplace concept of the test and its scientific definition of a test became markedly different [4]. In order to justify the quality of pedagogical measurements, their reliability and validity, the classical test theory was created, which was later called traditional, and was based on the concept of parallel measurements and correlation theory. On the basis of this theory

in the 30s-40s of the 20th century quantitative methods were intensively developed to analyze the quality of test tasks, standardized tests learning achievements and mastered the methods of scaling test results.

In the late 1940s, the fascination with pure theory was replaced by an understanding of the importance of the proper application of measurement in psychology and education. An important event for development of theory and practice of measurements in education in the late 1940's was the creation of Educational Testing Service (ETS) in the USA in 1947 [5]. Today this organization has its representations almost in all countries of the world. Among the tests created by ETS the most famous in connection with the expansion of educational exchange programs is TOEFL, which identifies proficiency levels in different types of speech activities for studying in English-speaking countries.

In the history of tests, there have been phases of ups and recessions. In particular, in the United States in the late 1960s the pedagogical tests were harshly criticized. There were expressed concerns that testing is an instrument of suppression of students' initiative and creativity, too simplified interpretation of such complex constructs as learning skills, and that it measured learning accomplishments incorrectly. There were other arguments against the widespread use of tests. Scientists-test researchers have been engaged mainly in constructive scientific criticism of traditional methods of test development, which led to the construction of a new theory, Item Response Theory (IRT), which often referred to today as modern test theory.

Undeniable advantages of IRT, such as the possibility of predicting the reliability of measurements, increasing the efficiency of testing and obtaining estimates of students' preparedness parameters, not depending on the difficulty of test items, have been widely used in practice since the late 1980s [5]. This became possible due to the development of algorithms for estimating the parameters of examinees and items based on mathematical IRT models, creation of software and wide use of PCs. The combination of the apparatus of classical theory and IRT in

test development opened up new opportunities for improving the quality of pedagogical measurements and application of testing in education.

The modern period in the history of test development is characterized by intensive development of IRT theory, creation of new models and methods of its application, introduction of computer technologies into testing, adaptive testing, various innovations in the field of test development and application. At the moment there are a number of research directions aimed at expanding the possibilities of pedagogical measurements, developing innovative meters and improving the quality of tests. These include the creation of new pedagogical measurement models, innovative forms of test items to test creative and practice-oriented aspects of student preparedness, methods of calibrating test items, and computer modeling techniques tests that ensure the planned accuracy of measurements. Much attention is paid to the psychological and pedagogical problems of testing (problems of anxiety, motivation), development of special procedures to identify the dimensionality of measurement space, the creation of special techniques, allowing a reasonable use of results of pedagogical measurements in education quality management.

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